

Colorimetric Estimation of Ce(IV) by Phenothiazines

R. T. SANKH* and A. B. AMBARDEKAR

Department of Chemistry, Ramnarain Ruia College, Matunga, Bombay-400 019

Manuscript received 6 March 1982, accepted 21 July 1982

SANKH Gowda and others¹ have reported a method of estimation of Ce(IV) by using fluphenazine hydrochloride as a complexing reagent. Our present investigation relates to the use of different phenothiazines as reagents for the spectrophotometric estimation of Ce(IV).

Experimental

Standard solution of Ce(IV) (100 ppm) was prepared by dissolving requisite amount of ammonium ceric nitrate in distilled water and was standardised by the method given in literature². 1% solutions of phenothiazines in methanol were prepared and used as reagents.

Procedure : To a solution containing 100 μg of cerium(IV) is added 0.5 ml of 1% ligand solution and mixed. The acidity of the mixture is adjusted between 2.4 to 4.0 molar with orthophosphoric acid in a total volume of 10 ml. The solution is diluted to 10 ml with distilled water and absorbance of the solution is recorded after 5 min at 510 nm. The amount of metal present in the solution is then determined from the calibration curve drawn under identical conditions.

The colour of the complex attains stability 5 min after the addition of reagent and is stable upto 25 min.

Physico chemical constants of the complexes have been summarised in Table I. Molar composition of the complexes were determined by Job's method of continuous variation³ and were found to be 1 : 1 (M : L) in all the cases.

TABLE I

Sl. No.	Reagent	Operative range from Ringbom's plot : $\mu\text{g}/\text{ml}$	Molar absorptivity $\times 10^{-3}$ lit. mole ⁻¹ cm ⁻¹	Sandell's sensitivity $\mu\text{g}/\text{cm}^2$
1.	Promethazine HCl	3.6 to 12.9	4.48	3.1×10^{-2}
2.	Pro-mazine HCl	5.6 to 12.9	5.61	2.5×10^{-2}
3.	Chlorpromazine	4.0 to 14.1	6.73	2.1×10^{-2}
4.	Thiopropazine mesylate	4.7 to 15.8	6.45	2.2×10^{-2}

The tolerance limits of various cations and anions are : Cd²⁺ (1 : 10); Ni²⁺ (1 : 8); Zr⁴⁺ (1 : 10); Cu²⁺ (1 : 10); Pb²⁺ (1 : 10); Fe²⁺ (1 : 10); U⁶⁺ (1 : 10); Mn²⁺ (1 : 10); Be²⁺ (1 : 10); Th⁴⁺ (1 : 10); Zn²⁺ (1 : 10); Ca²⁺ (1 : 10); Ba²⁺ (1 : 10); Cl⁻ (1 : 10); Br⁻ (1 : 10); SO₄²⁻ (1 : 10); NO₃⁻ (1 : 10); CH₃COO⁻ (1 : 10); ClO₄⁻ (1 : 8); B₄O₇²⁻ (1 : 10); MoO₄²⁻ (1 : 6); C₂O₄²⁻ (1 : 10).

It was found that cations such as Sn²⁺, Fe²⁺, As³⁺, V⁵⁺ and anions such as NO₂⁻, Fe(CN)₆⁴⁻, CNS⁻, S₂O₈²⁻, SO₃²⁻, BrO₃⁻ interfere seriously with the reaction.

Acknowledgement

The authors are grateful to Mr. A. Y. Dhamankar and Mr. U. R. Pandit for helpful discussions.

References

1. H. S. GOWDA, K. N. THIMMAIAH and B. N. ACHAR, *Rev. Roum. Chim.*, 1977, **22**, 745.
2. A. I. VOGEL, "Text Book of Quantitative Inorganic Analysis".
3. J. H. JOE and A. Z. JONES, *Ind. Eng. Chem., Anal. Ed.*, 1944, **16**, 111.

Spectrophotometric Determination of Ruthenium with Prochlorperazine Bismethanesulphonate

H. SANKH GOWDA* and A. THIMME GOWDA

Department of Post-graduate Studies and Research in Chemistry, University of Mysore, Manasagangotri, Mysore-570 006

Manuscript received 27 July 1981, revised 18 March 1982, accepted 8 July 1982

DURING the investigation on the reaction of phenothiazines with metal ions, prochlorperazine bismethanesulphonate, (PCPMS) 2-chloro-10-[3-(4-methyl-1-piperiziny) propyl] phenothiazine bismethanesulphonate, was found to give red colour with ruthenium(III) in phosphoric, sulphuric or hydrochloric acid. This reaction is now utilized for rapid spectrophotometric determination of ruthenium(III). The proposed method offers the advantages of simplicity, rapidity, sensitivity, reasonable selectivity and determination at room temperature without the need for extraction.

Experimental

Reagents and apparatus : A stock solution of ruthenium(III) was prepared by dissolving ruthenium(III) chloride (Johnson and Matthey, London) in dilute hydrochloric acid and diluting to 1 litre to give a solution of 1 M with respect to hydrochloric acid. The solution was standardized gravimetrically¹ and was further diluted to give a solution of 25 $\mu\text{g}/\text{ml}$. A 0.2% solution of PCPMS was prepared in double distilled water and stored in an amber bottle in a refrigerator. A Beckman Model DB spectrophotometer with matched 1 cm silica cells was used for absorbance measurements.

Procedure : An aliquot of the stock solution containing 5-205 μg of ruthenium(III) and 14 ml of 10 M phosphoric acid were transferred to a 25 ml volumetric flask, 3 ml of 0.2% PCPMS solution was added to this and the volume made upto the mark with double distilled water. The solutions were

mixed well and the absorbance was measured at 529 nm against the corresponding reagent blank prepared in the same manner. The amount of ruthenium in the sample solution was deduced from the standard calibration curve.

Results and Discussion

PCPMS readily forms red species with ruthenium(III) at room temperature (27°) in phosphoric, sulphuric or hydrochloric acid. The study of the red species, which is believed to be a radical cation^{3,8}, in sulphuric and hydrochloric acid media is not recommended because the reaction is less sensitive, less stable and many foreign ions interfere. Phosphoric acid was therefore selected for further studies. PCPMS and red species have the following structure.

The effect of varying the concentration of phosphoric acid was investigated. The rate of colour development and the sensitivity increase with increasing acid concentration from 0.5-5 M and then remain constant over the range 5-6 M (Fig. 1). The maximum colour development takes place instantaneously at room temperature in 5-6 M acid. An acid strength of 5.5 M of H₃PO₄ was chosen for all subsequent work. The absorbance of the red species remains constant for 90 min.

Fig. 1. Effect of H₃PO₄ concentration.

The absorption spectra of the reagent, ruthenium(III) and the red species in 5.5 M phosphoric acid are shown in Fig. 2. The red species exhibits maximum absorbance at 528-530 nm. The reagent and ruthenium(III) show little absorption at this wave length. Subsequent studies were made at 529 nm.

Beer's law was obeyed over the concentration range 0.2-7.3 ppm of ruthenium(III) with an optimum concentration range 0.7-6.9 ppm. The molar absorptivity was $1.17 \times 10^4 \text{ l. mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$. Sandell's

Fig. 2. Absorption spectra of reagent blank, ruthenium(III) and red species.

A. Reagent blank, B. Ruthenium(III) and C. Red species [Ru(III)=3 ppm, H₃PO₄ = 5.5 M].

sensitivity was estimated to be 8.6 ng cm⁻². The standard deviation calculated from 10 determinations on a solution containing 3 ppm of ruthenium was ± 0.025 .

The effect of reagent concentration was examined by measuring the absorbance of solutions containing 3 ppm of ruthenium(III) and varying amounts of PCPMS. A 12-fold molar excess of the reagent was necessary to produce maximum colour intensity. The optimum amount of 3 ml of 0.2% of the reagent solution was used. There is no appreciable change in the absorbance if the order of addition of reactants is varied. The absorbance values are not affected over the temperature range 10-52°. Above

TABLE 1—EFFECT OF DIVERSE IONS IN THE DETERMINATION OF Ru(III) (AMOUNT OF Ru(III) TAKEN, 8 ppm)

Ion added	Tolerance limit* ppm	Ion added	Tolerance limit* ppm
Fe(III)	4000	Pb(II)	260
Co(II)	150	V(V)	800
Cu(II)	1100	W(VI)	700
Ni(II)	1000	Ti(IV)	600
U(VI)	1300	Mn(II)	800
Zn(II)	1800	Ta(V)	2800
Mg(II)	2400	F ⁻	6000
Ag(I)	1.5	Cl ⁻	4000
Pd(II)	1.2	Br ⁻	1.2
Pt(IV)	35.0	I ⁻	4800
Au(III)	0.8	NO ₃ ⁻	10000
Os(VIII)	0.8	SO ₄ ²⁻	2800
Rh(III)	24.0	Acetate	1600
Ir(III)	18.0	Citrate	1500
Al(III)	1400	Oxalate	180
Mo(VI)	800	EDTA	1600
Zr(IV)	900	Tartrate	1600

* Amount causing an error of less than 2%.

52°, the absorbance gradually decreases with the rise in temperature.

The interference of several cations and anions which often accompany ruthenium were examined by carrying out determinations of 3 ppm of ruthenium(III) in the presence of each of these ions. Results in Table 1 show that PCPMS is selective for ruthenium(III), but Pd(II), Os(VIII), Au(III), V(V), Ag(I) and iodide interfere strongly. The nature of the red species was studied by passing an aliquot of the solution of the species through cation exchange resin, Dowex 50W-X8 and anion exchange resin Dowex 1-X8. The red species was retained by Dowex 50W-X8 and not retained by Dowex 1-X8. This indicated that the species is cationic.

Acknowledgement

The authors thank University Grants Commission, New Delhi, for the award of a Teacher Fellowship to one of them (A. T. G.) and Dr. L. Julou and Dr. J. Molle of Rhone-Poulenc Centre, Nicolas Grillet, Paris for the supply of pure PCPMS.

References

1. F. E. BEAMISH, "The Analytical Chemistry of Noble Metals", Pergamon Press, London, 1966, p. 250.
2. P. C. DWIVEDI, K. GURUDATH RAO, S. N. BHAT and C. N. R. RAO, *Spectrochim. Acta*, 1975, **31**, 129.
3. A. R. KATRITZKY and A. J. BOULTON (Eds), "Recent Advances in Chemistry of Phenothiazines-Advances in Heterocyclic Chemistry", Academic Press, New York, 1968, **9**, 821.

An Indirect Method for Iodometric Microdetermination of Certain Organic Acids

M. G. PATERIA and R. M. VERMA*

Department of Chemistry, University of Jabalpur, Jabalpur-482 001

Manuscript received 16 September 1981, revised 1 March 1982, accepted 8 July 1982

SINCE most carboxylic acids are weakly dissociated, their alkalimetry at micro level is confronted with two difficulties—poor inflection on the pH neutralisation curve which further contracts with increasing dilution of acid and alkali, and fading away of the phenolphthalein colour at the end-point¹.

Potentiometric location of the end-point is hampered owing to the formation of a buffer². The alkalimetry in non-aqueous medium has also been attempted using protophilic solvents, but in micro acidimetry the detection of the end-point is difficult.

* Author for correspondence.

Further, titrants such as sodium triphenylmethyl and lithium aluminium hydride are too unstable to be used as 0.01 N standards¹.

The present communication describes a micro procedure which consists of heating the acid sample with iodide and a known excess of potassium iodate solution and subsequent iodometric determination of the surplus iodate. The quantity of acid present in the test solution is calculated from the amount of iodate consumed. The quantitative reaction is accomplished only in 3-5 min even with samples containing as low as 0.025 meq of the different organic acids studied. In order to ascertain suitable experimental conditions for the determination, the effect of change in the amount of iodide and iodate and in the reaction period in the case of each acid has also been investigated. On the basis of the results of these preliminary experiments a general procedure applicable for determining 0.025-0.1 meq of certain organic acids has been worked out.

Experimental

Reagents: The following solutions were prepared using analytical grade chemicals and conductive water. 0.1 N (0.0166 M) potassium iodate, which was also used to standardize the sodium thiosulphate solution (0.1 N). 0.01 and 0.005 N solutions were obtained by suitable dilution of the 0.1 N solutions. 0.05 N solutions of mono-, di- and tri-chloroacetic, furoic, sulphamic, β -chloropropionic, isobutyric, fumaric and benzoic acids were prepared and standardized by alkalimetry and diluted suitably to prepare the test solutions. In addition, 10% potassium iodide, 4 N sulphuric acid and 1% aqueous starch solutions were also prepared.

Procedure: An aliquot of an acid solution containing 0.025-0.1 meq of the acid is pipetted into a 100 ml erlenmeyer flask and 10 ml of 10% potassium iodide and 5-20 ml of 0.01 N potassium iodate solution (about 100% excess) are added. The flask is then kept immersed in a boiling water bath for 3-5 min after which it is cooled immediately under tap. 1 ml of starch solution is introduced and thiosulphate solution is added dropwise with constant shaking until the decolourisation of the blue colour. About 2 ml of 4 N sulphuric acid is then added and the liberated iodine is titrated with 0.01 or 0.005 N thiosulphate. A blank is also run. The difference between the blank and the experimental titres gives the amount of iodate used up. From this, the quantity of the acid present in the assay solution is calculated using the following relationships.

1 ml of 0.01 N thiosulphate = 0.45 mg of COOH group.